

Achieving trustworthy, transparent and explainable AI for cybersecurity solutions

SPATIAL will tackle the identified gaps of data issues and black-box AI by designing and developing resilient accountable metrics, privacy-preserving methods, verification tools and system solutions that will serve as critical building blocks for trustworthy AI in ICT systems and cybersecurity.

Get to know more about the SPATIAL project!

Get to know what our partners have to say about trustworthy AI, ethics, cybersecurity, education, etc.

SPATIAL takes its orientation towards state-of-the-art concerns and practices and then targets practical use cases concerning AI in ICT systems and cybersecurity

[Interviews & pilots](#)

[Read more](#)

Our collaborations

We work with a range of parallel projects in common areas of research to maximise our impact and network reach. Check what they are doing within their projects!

[Read more!](#)

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